

Appendix

Table 1. Initial and final codes in the coding process (emerged codes in *Italics*).

1	Digital transformation and its role	How is digitalization described and how far it is developed in the company?
2	AI and deployment	How is AI understood and how is the deployment seen/described?
2.1	<i>AI understanding</i>	
2.2	<i>Deployment understanding</i>	
3	Role of AI in digitalization	How is the role of AI seen in the digitalization of the company?
4	AI built in strategy	Is AI built in the company strategy?
5	Approach for AI deployment	What is company vision, strategy, and operating model, i.e., the approach to AI deployment?
5.1	<i>Vision for AI</i>	
5.2	<i>Strategy for AI</i>	
5.3	<i>Operating model</i>	
6	Target functions and applications	How do you select the target functions and applications for deployment?
6.1	<i>Target functions</i>	
6.2	<i>Target applications</i>	
7	Investments and resources of deployment	Describe the investments and resources for AI deployment?
7.1	<i>Investments (funding)</i>	
7.2	<i>Resources (human)</i>	
8	Objectives for deployment	What objectives do you set for AI deployment?
9	Metrics for results and benefits	How do you measure the achievement of the objectives (the metrics)?
9.1.	<i>Results</i>	
9.2	<i>Benefits</i>	
10	The results and benefits achieved	What results and benefits have you achieved through AI deployment?
10.1	<i>Results (achieved)</i>	
10.2	<i>Benefits (achieved)</i>	
11	The enablers and capabilities	What key enablers and capabilities are needed for deployment and how do you develop them?
11.1	<i>Enablers</i>	
11.2	<i>Capabilities</i>	
11.3	<i>Development of enablers and capabilities</i>	
12	The obstacles and challenges	What are the key obstacles and challenges you have faced in the deployment?
12.1	<i>Obstacles</i>	
12.2	<i>Challenges</i>	
13	The learnings of deployment	What are the key learnings you have gained through deployment?
14	Importance of AI in 3-5 years	How do you see the importance of AI for the company in the next 3-5 years?
15	The role of TMT in the deployment	How do describe the role of TMT (top management team) in the deployment?
16	Strategy	How the role of AI in company strategy appears during the interview (interview perception)?